

Navigating EU-China Electric Vehicles Trade Disputes: A Game Theory Analysis

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Abstract

This paper investigates potential trade disputes stemming from environmental subsidies and competition in green technologies between China and the EU. Specifically, it analyzes the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles (EVs), examining the responses and strategies of the EU, specifically from Germany, and China, along with their respective EV manufacturers. In this regard, game theory is selected as a theoretical framework to explore the short and long-term impacts of these disputes on EU-China EV trade dynamics, predicting outcomes and strategic responses. The analysis finds that sustained bilateral cooperation and reciprocal market engagement between German and Chinese EV manufacturers constitute the most viable strategy for long-term mutual benefit, whereas escalating tariff measures tend to generate suboptimal, mutually detrimental outcomes.

Keywords: Trade disputes, environmental subsidies, electric vehicles (EVs), game theory analysis, strategic interactions

Introduction

Trade frictions between China and the EU over products in the sustainability sector have escalated recently, covering a wide range of industries, including photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine production. This scenario leads to fierce competition between the two parties, with both being major players in the field. For instance, in 2013, the EU imposed tariffs on Chinese PV products to protect domestic companies, arguing that Chinese products were sold below market prices with unfair

subsidies (Kanter & Bradsher, 2013).

This approach brought short-term gains. Despite temporary boosts for European PV companies, China supplied critical resources to Europe, including rare earth elements, and maintained its dominance. Chinese exports accounted for over 70% of global PV module production in 2013 and supplied key resources like rare earth elements to Europe (International Energy Agency, 2014). This trend is also evident in the lithium-ion battery industry, where Beijing controls essential segments of the global supply chain. According to EVTank data, China's lithium-ion battery shipments reached 887.4 GWh in 2023, representing 73.8% of the total global market share, a proportion that continues to increase (EVTank, 2024). In 2024, China's share of global EV sales increased from 64.8% in 2023 to 70.5%, further underscoring its dominant position in the industry (EVTank, 2025).

In response to concerns over overcapacity and unfair subsidization, the EU has imposed provisional countervailing duties on battery electric vehicles (BEVs) imported from China. The European Commission argues that the Chinese EV value chain benefits from distortive subsidies, posing a threat to fair competition, European automakers, and employment, while China regards the tariffs as an unreasonable trade barrier and maintains that its industry operates within WTO rules (European Commission, 2024). Thus, this paper investigates the EU's tariffs on Chinese EVs, analysing the responses and strategies of the EU, China, Germany, and their respective car manufacturers. Employing game theory, it explores how these tariffs impact trade patterns and structures among the EU, China, and Germany.

1. Background of EV tariffs in China

Europe's dependence on China for imports has increased over the past five years, rising from 22 % in 2017 to a peak of nearly 27 % in 2022, before leveling off at around 25 % in 2023 (Kratz et al., 2024). The 2% drop is underscored by fluctuations in trade deficits and surpluses in recent years (Matthes, 2024). Despite a temporary reduction in the overall trade deficit during the COVID-19 pandemic, the EU's dependence on Chinese imports remains significant. This dependence has become more pronounced amid efforts to diversify supply chains, especially after the Russia-Ukraine conflict. As a result, concerns associated with potential vulnerabilities in economic and trade relations with China have urged the EU to adopt a cautious approach (Sundari, 2024).

The automotive sector, including the electric vehicle (EV) industry, plays a pivotal role in this shifting dynamic. Engagement levels with China vary across EU Member States, reflecting divergent economic interests. This divergence was particularly evident when EU governments displayed split opinions on proposed tariffs for China-built EV imports. Germany, which maintains strong industrial ties with China in the EV sector, opposed the tariffs, while France, Italy, and Spain backed the measure (Blenkinsop, 2024). These differences reflect underlying disparities in the competitiveness of national automotive industries, which shape the fragmented policy preferences of EU Member States in the ongoing trade dispute with China over new energy vehicles (Ding et al., 2024).

The EU's strategic decisions on tariff escalation have critical strategic implications: balanced measures could support the domestic economy, inter alia, industries, and help sustain strong trade ties with Beijing amid evolving global dynamics. For Chinese EV manufacturers, Europe is the most important export destination, with the trend expected to

intensify (Sebastian, 2021). There is a growing trend among Chinese EV makers and suppliers to invest in European markets. For instance, Xpeng has entered the French market (Xpeng Motors, 2024), and BYD is building an EV plant in Hungary and eyeing another in Europe (Reuters, 2025).

Chery Auto is partnering with Spain's EV Motors to open a plant in Catalonia, and SAIC is searching for its first European plant. The world's largest battery maker, CATL, has ramped up production in Europe, with other Chinese battery suppliers aiding France in building its "battery valley" (Wu & Blenkinsop, 2024). The Kiel Institute for the World Economy estimates that punitive tariffs could reduce Chinese EV exports to Europe by a quarter, which might result in surges in automobile prices for consumers. The EU aims to balance the need for EVs with fair competition, encouraging China to reduce subsidies and overcapacity (Riegert, 2024). This is due to China's heavy use of subsidies that enable its manufacturers to produce electric vehicles at lower costs, which can lead to overcapacity and market imbalances, pressuring the EU to protect its own industries and consumers from unfair competition.

In his final year in office, President Biden initiated efforts to impose 100% tariffs on EVs from China, emphasizing the need for fair competition and addressing concerns over subsidies benefiting Chinese manufacturers (The White House, 2024). It is true that Biden's stance was partly aimed at bolstering his campaign for the 2024 U.S. presidential election, and is an example of a firm stance against China's economic threats (Sink, 2024). However, this policy also reflects a firm position he has held throughout his time in office, and is not a tactical shift influenced solely by electoral pressures. Most importantly, the effects of his policies extended beyond U.S.-China relations. The imposition of significant U.S. tariffs on Chinese EVs, for instance, had significant implications for European policies. It pressured the EU to reconsider its trade relations with China,

especially in sectors like EVs, where both regions compete globally (Tan, 2025). This created a situation where the EU was faced with potentially aligning with U.S. policies or strengthening its trade defense measures. Xi Jinping's visit to France in 2024 included significant meetings with President Emmanuel Macron and European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen, focusing on trade disputes, particularly China's dominance in the global EV market (Pineau et al., 2024). Discussions included potential tariff increases on Chinese EV imports to Europe. In this regard, the EU, led by von der Leyen, has expressed concerns about the impact of Chinese subsidies on EV production costs, potentially undermining European automakers' competitiveness. However, the absence of former German Chancellor Scholz during the visit pointed out internal EU divisions over trade policy towards China, particularly in the automotive sector. A strong economic relationship between Berlin and Beijing could be explained by major automakers like Mercedes-Benz, Volkswagen, and BMW, which operate plants in the mainland, emphasizing the importance of these relations (Sebastian, 2022). The divided stance notwithstanding, the German Minister for Economic Affairs and Climate at the time highlighted that there is a need for a unified, long-term strategy towards China (Reuters, 2024).

In response to concerns over Chinese EV industry subsidies, the EU initiated an anti-subsidy investigation in 2023. The findings reveal widespread complaints about unfair market access and significant industry overcapacity. Scholz suggested that the EU should avoid implementing EV tariffs, which could lead to a trade dispute with China. However, unsatisfactory negotiations led to the implementation of tariffs on EVs in April. In response, China levied tariffs on EU goods in May 2024, which raised concerns within the EU, particularly in Germany. German automakers hold significant market shares in

China, and the German government worried that tariffs on Chinese EVs could provoke retaliatory measures against German products. France also feared Chinese retaliation against its exports of wine and luxury goods. In early June 2024, the EU announced plans to impose additional tariffs on Chinese EVs to address market imbalance caused by Chinese subsidies. In June 2024, the EU announced plans to impose additional tariffs on Chinese EVs to address market imbalance caused by Chinese subsidies. The proposed tariffs ranged from 17.4% to 38.1%, with the final decision expected in early November (European Commission, 2023). This move marks the EU's largest subsidy investigation at the time, with the potential for significant economic retaliation from China. China retaliated by initiating an anti-dumping investigation into EU pork products, targeting primarily Spain, the Netherlands, and Denmark (Cash, 2024). In June 2024, former German Vice Chancellor Robert Habeck visited China and aimed to negotiate with Chinese officials, stressing that tariffs are necessary to offset unfair advantages from state subsidies (Cater, 2024). Habeck clarified that the EU tariffs are meant as compensatory rather than punitive, and expressed hope for political dialogue to avoid further escalation before the provisional measures take effect in July. However, skepticism remains about his ability to persuade Chinese officials of his version of the story.

Since Friedrich Merz officially assumed office as Germany's Chancellor in April 2025, the country's stance on EU-China electric vehicle (EV) tariffs has undergone a subtle but notable shift. Leading the Christian Democratic Union (CDU), Merz has placed greater emphasis on "reciprocal openness" and "industrial defense" in his economic policy. Under Chancellor Merz, Germany's China policy is entering a phase of cautious recalibration, with the Merz administration aiming to reduce strategic dependencies on China while preserving strong economic ties—a policy that is often described as "de-risking without decoupling" (Interesse, 2025).

In a public address, Merz stated that “Germany and Europe can no longer tolerate structural asymmetries in market access” (Rinke, 2025). This suggests that while Merz does not fully endorse the EU’s aggressive tariff policy, he also no longer opposes it as strongly as the previous administration. Instead, he appears to seek a new balance between safeguarding industrial security and maintaining economic ties with China. As the EU moves forward with its decision to impose countervailing duties of up to 38.1% on Chinese EVs—referring to provisional tariffs that the EU announced in June 2024 during its anti-subsidy investigation to penalize uncooperative companies, despite with the rate later adjusted to 35.3% in the final October decision— Merz’s government has adopted a more pragmatic approach. On the one hand, the government attempts to reassure German automakers that are concerned about losing Chinese market access; on the other, it aims to ensure that Germany does not appear weak within the EU in shaping trade rules. Merz’s government is also trying to stabilize Germany’s industrial base by strengthening external trade regulations, especially in the context of renewed U.S. tariffs under former President Trump’s return to office (Lunday, 2025).

Nonetheless, please note that as of 2024, when the core part of the analysis was drafted, the German government was still led by Chancellor Olaf Scholz under the “traffic light” coalition of the SPD, the Greens, and the FDP. As such, subsequent discussions may be unable to cover the direct influence brought by Merz’s policies.

2. The Basic Model of Game Theory in EU-China EV Tariff Dispute

Game theory is a framework for predicting behavior in competitive scenarios where one participant’s outcomes hinge on others’ decisions (Myerson, 1991). Originally used to analyze games and competitive strategies, it’s now essential across disciplines like

economics and political science. In economics, game theory models markets, strategic interactions among firms, and negotiations between buyers and sellers (Osborne, 2004). It illuminates decision-making based on expectations and strategic goals, facilitates equilibrium analysis, predicts outcomes in different scenarios, and informs predictions about negotiations and conflicts (Fudenberg et al., 1991). This article uses game theory to examine the strategic interactions among key players—the governments of China, the EU, and Germany, as well as major EV manufacturers on both sides—in response to the EU’s 2024 decision to impose tariffs on Chinese electric vehicles. By modeling these actors as rational decision-makers in a multi-stage game, this approach aims to capture how their choices influence each other’s outcomes and to predict possible responses and trade dynamics arising from this dispute. Each participant pursues their own interests and objectives. Strategic choices and reaction analyses are important aspects analyzed through game theory. The Prisoner’s Dilemma is a fundamental visual model within game theory that simplifies complex decision-making scenarios in international trade (Lewis, 2010).

Table 1
Game Theory Matrix: EU and China Raise or Lower Tariffs in the EV Tariff Dispute

	China Lower Tariffs	China Raises Tariffs
EU Lower Tariffs	EU: +1, China: +1	EU: +1, China: -1
EU Raises Tariffs	EU: -1, China: +1	EU: -1, China: -1

Note. Authors’ own visualization.

Take into account the EU-China interactions as an example here. It is a basic model where we assume that both parties are promoting tariff reductions during import and export, which is beneficial for market openness. In such cases, lowering tariffs is advantageous for the trade relationship between the two parties and is the most ideal approach in international trade, avoiding economic distortion. Conversely, any party raising tariffs results in a zero-sum game. In

the worst-case scenario, if both parties impose tariffs, especially punitive tariffs, it leads to a lose-lose situation. It is important to note that the above scenarios apply to any trade interactions between the EU and China, but the ideal state may not be realized in practice. The following game theory tables—related to EU-China government interactions, Germany-China government interactions, and Germany-China major electric vehicle negotiations, respectively—are all expansions and interpretations based on this foundational table.

Table 2
Game Theory Matrix: EU vs. China Tariff Strategies

	China Cooperates (Soft Response) (Jian, 2024)	China Retaliates (Hard Response)
EU Does Not Raise EV Tariffs	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
EU Raises EV Tariffs	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

This table illustrates various scenarios based on the decisions made by the EU and China regarding EV tariffs. In the first scenario, if the EU chooses not to increase EV tariffs and maintains its current approach, both parties benefit (+1, +1). This decision promotes increased trade opportunities and deeper cooperation between the EU and China. It also allows China to achieve its goal of avoiding additional EV tariffs, ensuring business continuity without significant tensions escalating. This outcome signifies a stable yet cautious interaction where both sides manage trade tensions carefully to prevent them from escalating into a full-scale trade conflict. This approach reflects the strategy adopted until July 2024, particularly following Chancellor Scholz and Minister Habeck's visit to China, where their influence in the EU persuaded other Member States to refrain from making definitive judgments on China until the tariffs officially were to take effect in November.

However, the EU may have also perceived a disadvantage, as it aims to maintain competitiveness within its market while balancing relations with China.

In the second scenario, if the EU decides to implement tariffs as a protective measure, two potential outcomes arise depending on China's response. Firstly, China opts not to retaliate immediately (-1, +1), preferring to continue negotiations and uphold international trade norms to resolve disputes. In the short term, the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese EVs serves as a protective measure for its domestic market. By increasing the cost of imported Chinese EVs, the EU aims to shield European manufacturers from competitive pressure. This protection allows domestic companies to invest in innovation and scale up production. Meanwhile, in the context of protecting market share and technological advantages, the EU's tariffs are designed to create a level playing field for European manufacturers. The EU seeks to enforce fair competition rules to ensure mutual benefits. However, increasing tariffs may harm the overall development of the EU's other industries dependent on China, such as French luxury brands, wine, and perfume, and Spain's pork industry, which may experience negative repercussions. Additionally, it can be seen that China executes a soft response and compromise, but the process doesn't stop. China doesn't retaliate with tariffs against the EU; it seems that China has downplayed the trade issue, but in the long term, it can still pursue other diplomatic avenues to balance this downplayed scenario. For example, China might exploit internal divisions within the EU regarding EV policies, seeking to align with non-EU countries like Norway or geopolitically China-friendly countries such as Hungary and Serbia, thus exacerbating EU internal disagreements. Regarding other European car manufacturers, those less connected to China are more supportive of increased tariffs. For instance, the joint venture between Stellantis (STLAM.MI) and Leapmotor (9863.HK) highlights how established automakers can view China as either a threat or

an opportunity (Wu & Blenkinsop, 2024). This approach will lead to more far-reaching impacts. In the long term, the EU may aim to diversify its supply chain and seek alternative production markets outside China to reduce dependency on Chinese imports. By broadening its economic partnerships, the EU not only mitigates the risk of over-reliance on a single source but also enhances its bargaining power in trade negotiations. Conversely, the second possible outcome (-1, -1) occurs if China chooses to retaliate with increased tariffs on key EU exports in response to EU tariffs. In this scenario, the EU faces economic repercussions as its exports to China become more expensive and less competitive. This escalation could lead to a detrimental trade conflict, resulting in economic losses for both the EU and China – a lose-lose situation that highlights the risks of escalating tariff disputes in international trade relations. For China, its primary objective is to reduce the high tariffs imposed by the EU on its EV products and expand its market share in Europe. In response to the EU's protectionist measures, China has implemented countermeasures such as increasing tariffs on EU products. This tit-for-tat strategy is characteristic of a repeated game, where each party's actions are contingent on the other's moves. The threat of retaliation serves as a deterrent, potentially forcing the EU to reconsider its tariff policies to avoid an escalating trade war. In the meantime, China considers enhancing economic ties with more China-friendly Eastern European countries represents a strategic move to bypass tariff barriers and maintain its market presence in Europe.

However, the final scenario (+1, -1) – where the EU does not impose tariffs (Open Market) and China retaliates (Hard Response) – though theoretically a Nash equilibrium, is unlikely to occur in reality, because the EU's imposition of tariffs is pivotal; should the EU abandon tariffs, China would likewise refrain from escalating retaliatory measures. The reasoning is that if

the EU decides to lift tariffs and open its market, China would have no incentive to impose retaliatory measures.

3. The German Government's Response to EU-China Tariff Dispute

In the ongoing tariff dispute between the EU and China, the German government faces significant implications due to its deep economic ties in the automotive sector with China. German automakers maintain significant exposure to the Chinese market, highlighting Germany's crucial role in EU-China trade dynamics.

In 2022, BMW delivered approximately 791,900 vehicles in China, including around 41,886 BEVs, accounting for about 5% of its Chinese sales (Lei, 2023). The most important markets for Mercedes-Benz Cars in 2023 were China with 36% of unit sales (Mercedes-Benz Group, 2023). Meanwhile, Volkswagen sold over 3.2 million vehicles in China in 2023, representing roughly 15% of its global sales (Oemisch, 2024). These numbers clearly show how closely connected German carmakers are to China, which plays a role in how Germany approaches the ongoing trade tensions between the EU and China.

Table 3
Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese Governments in the EV Tariff Dispute

	Chinese Government: Cooperate	Chinese Government: Defect (counter tariff measures)
German Government: Seek Compromise	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
German Government: Support EU Tariffs	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

In Scenario (+1, +1), both the German and Chinese governments seek a compromise and continue negotiations. This cooperative approach results in mutually beneficial outcomes, with both parties achieving positive payoffs. This is the

ideal scenario where both parties opt for more moderate strategies. Germany seeks a compromise, and China continues to cooperate with Germany, reaching an outcome where a trade war is avoided. Given Germany's substantial business stake in China, the government is also likely to push for negotiations that can lead to a mutually acceptable compromise. Recently, efforts by Habeck (Baden Württemberg International, 2024) and Scholz (Masengarb, 2024) in pushing forward have played a crucial role in addressing the EU's tariff dispute with China. This involves a mixed strategy, balancing defensive tariffs with diplomatic engagement. Germany must ensure that any protective measures do not escalate into a full-blown trade war, which could have broader economic repercussions. As a result, both sides benefit from maintaining stable economic relations and sharing mutual economic gains. German leaders are not only focused on domestic efforts but also exerting influence over other EU countries to reconsider the situation. For instance, in May 2025, Scholz was in discussions with Sweden and Hungary—which collectively hold over 50 percent of the EU seats—to explore opportunities to repeal the EV tariffs imposed on China. Scholz and Swedish Prime Minister Ulf Kristersson are actively working to influence EU internal policies aimed at mitigating the tariff impacts (Agence France-Presse, 2024). Afterward, new proposals have surfaced within EU-China trade talks to replace punitive tariffs with a minimum pricing scheme for Chinese-made EVs. According to a report in April 2025, this compromise could de-escalate the trade tensions by setting floor prices for imported Chinese vehicles rather than imposing rigid duties. This approach is gaining traction among EU officials as a more sustainable and balanced policy option (Jessen, 2025).

In Scenario (-1, +1), while Germany supports EU tariffs, China chooses to continue negotiations rather than retaliate. Despite indications that the German government

generally opposed tariffs, as they could lead to economic losses, it cannot be ruled out that Germany, having failed to mediate within the EU, is forced to “support” the EU's decision to impose additional tariffs. Such conflicting behaviors may stem from small parties with fewer seats, like AfD (Alternative for Germany), conflicts within Germany, where certain factions in parliament openly support tariffs similar to the EU, citing trade protectionism to safeguard domestic automotive industries. However, due to the German traffic coalition government, their influence to enforce effectively remained constrained. Looking ahead, Germany's strategy may prioritize reducing dependency on China while safeguarding its economic interests. To mitigate the risks associated with excessive reliance on China, Germany could pursue diversification of trade partnerships and production bases. This strategic shift resembles a multi-stage game, wherein Germany invests in alternative markets to establish new equilibria that enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability. By diversifying economic interests, Germany aims to bolster its negotiating power and resilience in future trade disputes. Balancing protectionist measures with the promotion of open markets is crucial, necessitating a cooperative approach to establish equitable competition rules that benefit all stakeholders. On the other hand, China opts to negotiate rather than retaliate. Although this appears to be a positive move to keep the market open in the short term, it indicates that the reliability of German-Chinese EV businesses is too strong to abandon. As a result, the Chinese government needs to win over the German side to withstand significant tariff pressures and maintain cooperation with German EV manufacturers. This represents a highly unequal trade relationship, which is unsustainable in the long run.

In Scenario (+1, -1), the German government seeks a compromise, but China implements retaliatory tariffs, which is the same as the EU-China scenario (+1, -1). However, this scenario seems unlikely, as China's position indicates that as long as the EU reverses tariffs without

hindering the development of China's EV industry, punitive measures against other EU industries would not be necessary.

In Scenario (-1, -1), the German government supports the EU's imposition of tariffs on Chinese EVs, prompting the Chinese government to retaliate with tariffs on EU products. This could escalate into a trade war, resulting in significant economic losses for both parties. Germany, heavily reliant on the Chinese automotive market, faces severe repercussions, leading to negative outcomes for both sides (-1, -1). Germany maintains market access but loses bargaining power, as China might no longer trust Germany's influence within the EU. Despite appearing to protect its domestic EV market to some extent in the short term, Germany forfeits future cooperation opportunities with China and fails to reach a consensus in negotiations. Moreover, Germany not only loses its advantageous market share in China but also suffers a devastating blow to its GDP and domestic job positions. On the other hand, China's retaliatory measures harm its own consumers, particularly affecting products like wine and pork. Amid China's economic slowdown, tariff implementation further clouds consumer confidence.

4. Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese EV Manufacturers on the EU-China Tariff Dispute

Suppose that the main EV manufacturers on the German side include BMW, Mercedes-Benz, and Volkswagen (excluding small and medium-sized German EV companies, which have a smaller share in China and are relatively less relevant to international trade). On the Chinese side, the focus is on purely domestic brands such as SAIC, BYD, and Geely, with Tesla not included due to its unique position. In this context, the most likely strategies for German car manufacturers are twofold: accelerating localization efforts in China, such as hiring local managers and

deepening their presence in the Chinese market, or searching for other markets and attempting to replace the Chinese market to diversify their supply chains worldwide. Meanwhile, Chinese manufacturers are considering two strategies: cutting profit margins to preserve competitive advantages and increasing investments in Germany or bearing the negative results of possible EU anti-subsidy investigations, abandoning the German market, and expanding their presence in other export markets. Both sides are engaged in strategic maneuvers to protect and enhance their market positions amidst evolving trade dynamics and regulatory environments. According to the analysis of the EU-China government game theory matrix above, there are two possible scenarios for German and Chinese EV manufacturers.

4.1 The First Scenario: EV Tariffs Ease

The first scenario is EU-China (+1, +1): Germany successfully mediates, completely convincing the EU not to impose tariffs on China while China also refrains from taking retaliatory measures.

Table 4
Game Theory Matrix: German and Chinese Manufacturers in the EV Tariff Dispute

	Chinese Manufacturers: Cooperate (Expand Market in Germany)	Chinese Manufacturers: Defect (Search Other Markets)
German Manufacturers: Cooperate (Localization or Expand Market in China)	(+1, +1)	(+1, -1)
German Manufacturers: Defect (Search Other Markets)	(-1, +1)	(-1, -1)

Note. Authors' own visualization.

4.1.1 Scenario (+1, +1)

This represents the optimal outcome for both

parties. When Chinese and German manufacturers cooperate, they maintain competitiveness and expand their market presence. This mutual cooperation allows growth and prosperity. In the short term, both benefit from expanded market access and sustained competitiveness. This sets the stage for long-term competition, fostering innovation and growth in the global market. However, this may lead to losses for small and medium-sized German enterprises. By focusing on market expansion and maintaining competitive advantages, both sides ensure ongoing development and penetration. Short-term gains include access to new markets and increased investments. Over time, both profit from diversified market access and significant investments.

4.1.2 Scenarios (+1, -1) and (-1, +1)

Whether it is German manufacturers expanding in China and Chinese manufacturers giving up in Germany, or German manufacturers giving up the Chinese market to seek other markets while Chinese manufacturers invest further in Germany, these scenarios do not exist without tariffs. In the case of successful negotiations, German manufacturers would not abandon their advantages in China, and China would not give up the German market. Moreover, the German government's credibility in mediating would significantly increase, bolstering confidence between German and Chinese car manufacturers and promoting rational and stable investment behaviors.

4.1.3 Scenario (-1, -1)

Both sides mutually abandoning investment in each other's markets is clearly non-existent. In the short term, they remain in a honeymoon phase of cooperation. Looking ahead, following this mediation turmoil, this opens up the possibility that some car manufacturers may reassess their geopolitical strategies and shift focus to other markets. Chinese manufacturers

might view the avoidance of tariffs this time as a temporary reprieve, but they could anticipate future challenges. This could potentially lead to divergences from each other's markets, though this remains a low-probability scenario.

4.2 The Second Scenario: EV Tariffs Escalate

The second scenario is EU-China (-1, +1) or (-1, -1): Germany's mediation fails, resulting in the EU imposing tariffs on China, while China either refrains from or implements retaliatory measures. Regarding the imposition of tariffs and whether the Chinese government imposes punitive tariffs on the EU, these punitive measures do not directly impact German EV manufacturers since the targeted industries are not in the German EV sector but wine, luxury or pork businesses for France and Spain. Therefore, the investment behaviors of German EV companies remain unaffected.

4.2.1 Scenario (+1, +1)

The third scenario is (+1, +1): German manufacturers expand in China and Chinese manufacturers expand in Germany. Although tariffs increase costs for German manufacturers and make market expansion in China less promising, some expectations persist, preventing them from fully abandoning the Chinese market. According to current surveys, despite the anticipation of tariffs, German manufacturers cannot quickly abandon the Chinese market. Instead, they are adopting a localization strategy to focus more on local production, sales, and profits (Baur, 2024). For instance, major German DAX companies such as Siemens and BASF have accelerated their localization processes. Siemens is not solely relying on China; while enhancing its localization efforts in China, such as the Marco Polo project in Sichuan, it is also shifting its focus towards Singapore. Similarly, BASF continues to increase its investments in China, undertaking its fifth major investment in Zhanjiang, Guangdong (Zhang & Shi, 2023). Despite many problems both within and outside China, more than a third (38%) of German companies, according to the

survey, remain optimistic and anticipate an improvement in the economic situation. Nearly half do not expect any change, and 16% foresee a deterioration. Only approximately 25% of the surveyed companies projected an increase in profits for the year 2024. In the next two years, just over half intend to increase their investments in China (German Press Agency, 2024). Additionally, for China, continuing to expand in the German market after the imposition of tariffs is detrimental, especially as Chinese firms lose their competitive edge due to compliance with anti-subsidy regulations. Chinese firms must adapt to new regulatory environments and work to regain their competitiveness in the international market. However, given Germany's leading position in the automotive industry, particularly in innovation and technology, and the worsening economic relationship between China and the US, cooperation with Europeans, especially Germans, is crucial. This is evident from the series of agreements signed between the Chinese government and large German car companies during Scholz's visit to China earlier in April 2024. Even with EV tariffs, it is challenging for Chinese EV manufacturers to quickly abandon their cooperation with German ones. Therefore, despite mutual harm and the distortions caused by tariffs, it remains a win-win situation. In the long run, it can benefit the global electric vehicle market by sharing human resources and technology, thereby enhancing the overall competitiveness of the industry.

4.2.2 Scenarios (+1, -1) and (-1, +1)

Although in both scenarios, the imposition of tariffs does not significantly alter the presence of German EV manufacturers in the Chinese market or Chinese manufacturers in the German market. Whether German manufacturers continue to expand in China while Chinese manufacturers withdraw from Germany, or German manufacturers exit China while Chinese ones continue to invest in

Germany, these situations are rare under tariff implementation. Tariffs are merely policy directives and do not profoundly impact the entire Sino-German EV supply chain.

However, in the case of unsuccessful negotiations with the EU, the capacity of the German government is not only questioned by German manufacturers but also creates unease among Chinese ones. Therefore, with negotiations failing, both sides lose their sense of economic predictability, destabilizing mutual investment behaviors. This instability is particularly evident in the long term, where it represents a dual play or transitional strategy, influenced largely by the underlying mistrust between China and Germany amid efforts to mitigate risks. Both sides are forced to seek alternative markets to avoid greater geopolitical risks, with tariffs playing a supporting role rather than a primary one. Chinese manufacturers, by focusing on expanding their reach into new markets in Norway (which is exempt from EV import tariffs), Asia, Latin America, and Africa, reduce their dependence on the EU market. Therefore, in the long run, both German and Chinese manufacturers will build a more diversified global market presence. This strategic diversification enables them to mitigate risks associated with over-reliance on any single market.

4.2.3 Scenario (-1, -1)

Both sides mutually abandon each other's markets. In the scenario where tariffs are imposed, based on current practices of German manufacturers, even if the EU imposes tariffs and German government mediation fails, German manufacturers would scale back their operations in China to some extent, while Chinese manufacturers would correspondingly reduce their activities in Germany. This results in a lose-lose situation. Lastly, if both Chinese and German manufacturers choose to defect, the result is a lose-lose situation (-1, -1). Both sides suffer from diminished competitiveness and market presence, illustrating the detrimental effects of defection on both parties.

In summary, whether the EU successfully avoids EV tariffs or not, the win-win situation for Sino-German businesses lies in continuing to invest in each other's markets, while the lose-lose scenario arises from diverging from this path. Some German manufacturers remain optimistic about the Chinese market, especially in the short-term outlook for the EV market. However, under a risk-averse backdrop, some companies may harbor concerns about potential tariff losses and geopolitical risks, leading them to consider scaling back their presence in China. Concurrently, Chinese manufacturers would integrate and diversify their supply chains in response to competitors' actions. Nevertheless, this dynamic remains a zero-sum game, offering no benefits to the overall development of the EV industry. The inefficiencies caused by tariffs are challenging to resolve. In essence, on this issue, German and Chinese manufacturers alike, regardless of their strategic choices, will suffer as victims of EV tariff policies.

Conclusion

This article employs game theory to analyze the potential interactions between the EU, Germany, and China in the context of the EU levying additional duties on Chinese EVs. It also examines the responses and strategies of these actors following the tariff implementation, drawing an analysis of the resulting outcomes.

Based on the analysis, we conclude that the optimal scenario would ideally involve the EU refraining from imposing tariffs on Chinese EVs to avoid triggering retaliatory measures from China, as tariffs can distort trade for both parties. Given the current state of affairs, it is evident that this has not occurred. Therefore, to mitigate additional negative consequences, the next best approach would be for the EU to incrementally impose tariffs on Chinese EVs, recognizing the zero-sum nature of the situation. This measured strategy aims to

balance protecting domestic industries with maintaining stable trade relations, albeit within a competitive framework. For the German government, as a pivotal player in both the EU and Chinese markets, the challenge lies in navigating these tensions while securing its automotive sector's competitiveness and future growth. The best way is to engage in negotiations aimed at mitigating the risks associated with tariffs. From the Chinese perspective, the government has implemented retaliatory tariffs but has also shown a willingness to negotiate with Germany, acknowledging the need for cooperation in EV development amid strained relations with the US. This approach will undergo constructive dialogue that balances economic interests and minimizes potential disruptions to bilateral trade relations. German and Chinese manufacturers should continue expanding their presence in their respective markets to counter protectionist measures, aiming to sustain mutual economic benefits and foster ongoing growth and cooperation in the global EV market.

Looking ahead, the resolution of these disputes will likely hinge on diplomatic negotiations and strategic compromises that balance protectionist measures with maintaining open and fair global trade. The game theory analysis suggests that increased tariffs harm the interests of most stakeholders. The focus should be on sustainable strategies for engaging with China, the world's largest EV stakeholder, rather than relying on short-term tariff solutions.

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